

THE GENEALOGY OF UMAR SHAIKH MIRZA AND HIS CHILDREN ZAKHIRIDDIN MUKHAMMAD BABUR MIRZA

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8176528>

Annotation: This article provides information about the Timurid ruler Umarshaikh Mirza and his brief life, his wives, children, and the brief life of Zakhiriddin Mukhammad Babur, the most brave and unique talent among his children, family members.

Keywords: Timurids, Fergana, Andijan, Akhsikent, Umarshaikh Mirza, Zakhiriddin Mukhammad Babur, Baburnoma, Khamsa, Masnavi, Khumayunnoma, Baburis, Kabul, Agra.

There are dynasties in history that many nations are unaware of, but there are also dynasties that founded science and culture, which are preserved in the memory, works, and legends of all nations. The great Master Amir Temur, who shook the earth in his time, and his grandson Mirzo Ulugbek, who made a great contribution to the development of astronomy and mathematics, Khusayn Baykara, and one of the representatives of the last Timurids, Zakhiriddin Mukhammad Babur, who built a state in India, are the great representatives of the family of the so-called Timurid dynasty. They not only created the political and economic foundations of their country, but also developed science for mankind.

Zakhiriddin Mukhammad Babur was born on February 14, 1483 in Andijan, the then capital of the Ferghana Valley. His father Umarshaikh Mirza was born in Samarkand in 1455 and tragically died in Akhsi fortress in 1494. It is written in "Boburnoma" that Umarshaikh Mirza was a well-educated ruler and read the books "Khamsa" and "Masnavi" a lot. Babur Mirza's mother, Kutlughnigorkhanim, was the daughter of Yunus Khan, the governor of Tashkent, who was of Genghis descent. Umarshaikh Mirza had three sons and five daughters, Babur Mirza was the eldest son. Umarshaikh Mirza's great teacher was the famous Khwaja Ubaidullakh Akhrar Vali. Khoja Akhror Umarshaikh called Mirza "my son". That is why Umarshaikh Mirza asked his piri Khwaja Akhrar Vali to give him a name when he had his first son, and his teacher named the baby Zakhiriddin Mukhammad [1. - P. 95.]. Many positive qualities of Umarshaikh Mirza - his literacy and generosity, nobility, and most importantly, his justice and faith - contributed to the upbringing of Babur Mirza from his youth. In "Baburnoma", Babur Mirza writes about his father: he was born in Samarkand in 860 Hijri, he was the fourth son of Sultan Abu Said Mirza from his wife Shakhsultanbegim, and he first gave him Kabul as his property, and he also gave him control over Ferghana region [1. - P. 466.].

In 1485, Umarshaikh Mirza's brother Sultan Ahmed Mirza gathered an army to capture Tashkent. Umarshaikh Mirza asks his father-in-law Yunus Khan for help in exchange for Sairam. The parties are drawn towards each other. Peace is concluded through the mediation of Khoja Ubaidullakh Akhror. According to the peace agreement, Tashkent will be given to Yunus Khan. In 1494, when Babur Mirza's uncle Sultan Makhmud Khan made an alliance with Sultan Akhmad and marched his army on Andijan, Umarshaikh Mirza fell and died in his fortress with his dovecote in the city of Akhsi.

Umarshaikh described Mirza's appearance in "Boburnoma" as follows: "...he was a short man, with a smooth beard, many faces, and a lazy man. He wore a turban too tight, and when tying a bag, he pulled his stomach in to tie it". Babur's father explained as follows about his faith

and knowledge: he was a Hanafi sect, a man of pure faith, he used to pray five times a day, and he had completed his lifetime punishments. Khazrat Khvaja Ubaidullakh had great respect for Vali, he used to be a frequent visitor to his conversations, and Khazrat Khvaja also called him his son. He was fluent in literature, he read “Khamsatayn”, religious books and history, he often read “Shakhnoma”. He had a talent for verse, but he did not care about poetry [2. - P. 10.]. The following information is given in “Boburnoma” about Umarsheikh Mirzo’s generosity and justice: “... his justice was high, when the Chinese caravan was coming, snow fell from the mountains east of Andijan and crushed the caravan of a thousand camels, two people survived. When he found out about this, he sent inspectors and found the entire caravan, found the governors from Samarkand and Khurasan and handed over the goods to them. He was generous, kind and sweet”.

In the work, the following was given about the wives and children of Umarshaikh Mirza: Mirza had three sons and five daughters. The eldest of his sons was Babur Mirza, the wife of Umarshaikh Mirza was from Kutlugh Nigorkhanim, the daughter of Yunus khan. Another son was Jakhangir Mirza, who was two years younger than Babur Mirza, from his wife Fatima Sultan, who was the daughter of Umarshaikh Mirza’s Mongolian nobles. Another son was Nasir Mirza. He was four years younger than Babur Mirza, his mother was Umidabegim Gunchachi from Andijan (“gunchachi” was a concubine or temporary wife given to the Sultan). One of the five daughters of Umarshaikh Mirza, Khonzodabegim was the eldest. She was born in 1478. The other two princesses, Mekhribonbegim and Shakharbonubegim, were the children of Nasir Mizo. Another daughter was Yodgor Sultanbegim, her mother Agha Sultan was a horse rider, and another daughter was Rukiya Sultanbegim, her mother was Makhdum Sultanbegim, she was called Karakozbegim. [2. - P. 13.].

Father’s upbringing played an important role in determining Babur Mirza’s future. Babur Mirza was just and generous following the example of his father. After the death of his father, 12-year-old Bobur Shaykh Mazidbek, Bobokuli Boboalibek, and Kasim Kavchin manage the administration. Babur Mirza constantly fought for the throne, captured Samarkand in 1497, 1500, 1501, Osh and its surroundings in 1502-1503, and was defeated by Akhmad Tanbal. In 1503, Babur captured Kabul and Ghazna without a fight. In 1506, Babur’s mother Kutlugh Nigorkhanim died. When Babur is in Samarkand, he communicates with Alisher Navoi by letter, but he does not have the chance to meet.

As a result of Mukhammad Shaibani khan’s pressure, Babur retreated towards India and made five campaigns to India starting from 1507. On April 12, 1526, in the Battle of Panipat, his army of 12,000 men defeated the 100,000-man army of the Indian sultan Ibrahim Lodi and thus founded the dynasty known as the Babur Empire in North India, and this empire became known as the Great Moghuls in Europe [3. - P. 298.]. Babur Mirza died on December 26, 1530 in Agra. He was buried in the center of Nurafshan Park on the left bank of the Jamna River. In 1533, the Khoki was transferred to Kabul (“Baghi Babur”), contrary to his will.

Babur’s place in history is not only that he founded a new dynasty in India as a great leader, but also that his great service left the “Baburnoma” to the generations. In “Boburnoma”, Mirza Babur described the events he saw and knew year by year. This work was originally called “Event”. Later, it arrived under the names “Vaqoe’ Boburiy”, “Tuzuki Boburiy”, “Boburnoma”. In addition, he wrote “Mukhtasar” about Babur’s aruz weight, “Mubayyin” about the rules of

Islam and the tax system of that time, and invented a new alphabet – “Khatti Baburi” - which sought to make the reading of the Arabic alphabet easier [4. -P. 353.].

Babur Mirza had a total of nineteen children, of whom only seven reached adulthood, the rest died young. According to the work “Khumayunnama”, after Babur Mirza married Aisha Sultanbegim, the 17-year-old daughter of Sultan Akhmad Mirza, at the age of 23, he had a daughter named Fakhriya Sultanbegim, but she died in infancy. After Babur Mirza took Kabul in 1504, Mokhimbegim gave birth to King Khumayun, Borbol Mirza, Mehr Jakhanbegim, Eshan Davlatbegim and Farrukh Mirzas. Then Sultan Ahmad Mirza’s daughter Masuma Sultanbegim had a daughter. Masumabegim died during childbirth and they named her daughter after her. Another wife of Babur Mirza, Gulrukh Begim, gave birth to Kamran Mirza, Askari Mirza, Shahrukh Mirza, Sultan Akhmed Mirza and Gulzor Begim. Among his wives, Gulrangbegim, Gulchekhrabegim, Khindol Mirza, Gulbadanbegim and Olur Mirzos were born to the noble and well-mannered Dildar Beg [5. -P. 98.]. In 1519, when Babur Mirza conquered Bujur (Pakistan), he married the daughter of one of the Afghan emirs, Avghani Ogacha, but there is no information about his children. It is said that this woman was the queen of the Yusufzai tribe of Afghans and was the daughter of Shakh Mansur, the brother of the tribal leader Malik Ahmed. Through the marriage of this princess, the relationship of this tribe with Babur Mirza will improve. Babur forgives Malik Akhmed, who wanted to kill Mirza. The original name of the princess is Bibi Mubarika, and it is said that she is unequaled in beauty [6. -P. 179.]. Thus, the genealogies of Umarshaikh Mirza and Babur Mirza consisted of these. As history repeats itself, Babur Mirza, the first son of Umarshaikh Mirza, Khumayun Mirza, the first son of Babur Mirza, and Akbar Mirza, the first son of Khumayun Mirza, extended the dynasty tree. The next generations of these individuals made the so-called “Baburi” state in India one of the largest empires in the world.

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